

DIDACTIC REQUIREMENTS FOR THE FORMATION OF LEARNING MOTIVATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This thesis describes the specific aspects of the formation of interest in examples of fiction literature in elementary school students through reading. Also, the article suggests that knowledge-based interests are a motive that ensures personal activity, and that it contributes to the development of cognitive activity.

Keywords: young students, reading, examples of fiction, interest, study subjects.

INTRODUCTION

Today, there are many directions and means of personal empowerment. Such tools primarily serve to expand the cognitive capabilities of each person. Interest in books and reading ensures the effective course of personal activity. That is why it is of particular importance to form interest in fiction in students through reading.

In the encyclopedia of pedagogy, "Interest - 1) awareness of an object or event and a tendency to master a type of activity; 2) attitude of a pupil or student to a certain thing and event that is valuable and pleasant for him" [1] is defined as.

MAIN PART

Interests embody the unique characteristics of a person. Curiosity helps to acquire knowledge consciously, carefully, steadily, with awareness. Curiosity serves to form desire, activity, internal motivation and need in a person. Curiosity is manifested in a person's selective attitude to existence, making unique decisions, self-control, striving for a goal, and overcoming obstacles. That is why it is of particular importance to arouse interest in this or that phenomenon in students starting from the primary grades. Because of curiosity, students seek to master a particular subject more deeply. They begin to acquire knowledge about him with special aspiration.

By instilling interest in fiction among elementary school students, wider conditions are created for them to study knowledge and life experiences expressed in rare examples of human intelligence. Reading serves as the main tool in creating interest in fiction in students.

According to R. G. Safarova[2], the educational process plays a key role in arousing interest in fiction among students. Today, when the task of harmonious development of personality is set before the educational process, it is becoming a socio-pedagogical necessity to arouse interest in fiction literature in students with the help of books. By reading books, students can improve their knowledge regularly. Due to the increase in information technology and sources of information, students turn to books less and less. From the first days of interaction with students, teachers should arouse interest in fiction. It is in primary grades that students' interest in fiction becomes stable and strengthens throughout their lives.

The great Czech pedagogue Ya. A. Komensky[3] is the founder of the idea of arousing interest in fiction literature among students. In his work "Great didactics", he thought about how to arouse interest in students in this or that activity.

Interest is a form of manifestation of cognitive needs. It directs a person to realize the purpose of his activity. It encourages a deeper understanding of the essence of the evidence that represents objective existence. Interest represents a person's desire to master the object of study. Satisfying one interest of the student is the basis for the emergence of the second interest and creates conditions for the development of cognitive activity.

According to LS Vygotsky[4], interests are the driving force of child behavior. It is a vivid expression of the student's aspirations. With the help of interests, students' activities are tailored to their needs. Therefore, the educational process should be organized based on the interests of students. This means that the educational process is organized on the basis of giving priority to the subjects of interest to the students. It is not possible to attract the student to learn a certain phenomenon by putting pressure, threats, and threats on the student. It is important to arouse the interest of students, as well as to direct it to a specific goal.

Another important point is to bring learning processes closer to life situations, taking into account the interests of students. Examples of fiction literature play an important role in bringing the learning process closer to life situations. Bringing the learning process closer to real life situations makes students interested in certain events. Educators should realize that by arousing interest in students, they can be more involved in a specific activity.

Each person has an experience of a personal attitude towards the existence that surrounds him. It is this attitude that brings him to certain situations and creates interest, need and desire to learn certain things.

Cognitive interests help to ensure the dynamic development of the learning process. It helps students to actively master learning activities. Curiosity about learning creates initiative in students. In this process, the student himself is looking for ways to acquire new knowledge. As a result, the effectiveness of education, training and development increases. Teachers should have a strong influence on students who are not active and are not interested in anything, and direct their interest in learning to a specific goal.

Interests have the potential to evoke vivid emotions in students. In order to satisfy their curiosity, students are required to study the objective existence in depth, to understand its specific aspects. As a result of satisfying students' interests, they have a sense of joy and a desire to learn more. If students can't learn something they are interested in, they develop negative feelings and lack of confidence in their abilities. Curiosity about knowledge is one of the main motivations for reading. Students like it more than others. It starts from the moment when students decide what is interesting for them and what is not interesting. These may include a lesson, a subject, or specific books.

For students, learning interests as motivations for learning motivate them to learn about these objects. In this case, the teachers cannot prevent them, because it is related to the personal interests of the students. It expresses the main goal of the students' activity, ensures that the learning process is easy, effective, bright, full of emotions, and creates a basis for them not to get tired in classes. Interests related to knowledge are interrelated with various inclinations of educational activity and contribute to comprehensive enrichment of the student's worldview. When these interests are not aligned, students' development processes are slow. As a result of formation of students' interest in certain phenomena, they develop a conscious attitude towards the educational process. This, in turn, helps students to manage their personal educational activities, to clearly understand the ways and goals of achieving the set goal. In addition, it ensures the regular enrichment of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the field of their interest.

According to O.A. Torakulova [5], formation of students' interest in knowledge is one of the difficult tasks of the teacher. For this, the pedagogue should organize the educational process in the direction of forming the students' interest in learning. In this process, it is desirable for the student to be regularly

interested in educational materials, to develop himself, to expand the direction and fields of acquired knowledge. It is also important that students make their personal contribution to solving problems that arise during the learning process.

To achieve this goal, the teacher is required to overcome many problems that arise in the pedagogical process, to choose the best methods of organizing the lesson. For this, the teacher selects the necessary educational materials, analyzes various approaches to the formation of independence in students, determines the result of the achievement of the educational goal.

Satisfying students' interests not only enriches their intellectual fields, but also has the ability to direct them to future activities.

The following levels can be distinguished in the field of development of students' interest in knowledge:

meticulous curiosity

interest based on personal knowledge creative interest.

They represent various interests of students in relation to one or another educational subject. These include the desire to learn new knowledge, assimilation of new information.

Inquisitiveness is the first stage of cognitive curiosity. In this way, his desire to learn and know certain things is expressed in a way related to the student's attention. At this stage of interest, a particular object or phenomenon is not studied in depth, but is carefully looked at. In this case, a person begins to carefully study what changes have taken place in the reality around him and gives an appropriate response to it.

Interests at this stage are not regular, but have an elemental character and arise depending on an unfounded situation. This situation is observed especially in the first days when students come to school. Such observations of students depend on some things around them and acquire a superficial character. 3rd-4th graders are curious about the things around them.

The curiosity-based stage of curiosity acquires a new essence, and the desire to determine all the specific aspects of the phenomena and things that interest him increases. In this process, learning is goal-oriented, and students' aspirations are influenced by external factors. At the stage of curiosity, it is possible to observe the formation of a desire for direct interest in students. In this, the student is fully involved in the learning process. With its help, he satisfies his knowledge needs. The result of such activity is of special importance for the student. As a result, the student begins to study the field he is interested

in more deeply, and does not stop at one point. Curiosity becomes personal interest.

Knowledge-based interest creates the need to form causal connections. As a result, students begin to try to determine the specific characteristics of this connection. At this stage, students are presented with certain problems. And students strive to find solutions to these problems in a conscious way. Knowledge-based interests lead students away from ignorance. Awareness of new aspects of objective existence ensures that they rise to new levels of intellectual development. As a result, students' active actions are ensured: self-control, belief in willpower, initiative and optimism in the work process, manifestation of ownership of the desire for self-improvement and development.

The stage of manifestation of creative interests includes the following: independence, the student's reshaped activity, the use of methods that provide new solutions to the problems in front of him, and the manifestation of his creative abilities.

Interest in reading is an interest that expresses the desire of students to learn the experience of their ancestors expressed in books and apply it in their work. For this, students should be mentally and emotionally active. Mental and emotional activity appears in books as a goal-oriented main component, which serves to provide students with a social experience. Because books preserve this experience and present it from ancestors to generations. Accordingly, knowledge-based interests are choice-based interests that primarily contribute to the development of students' intellectual domains. With the help of interest, students actively engage in mastering knowledge in a particular field. The book will help them in this.

CONCLUSION

The importance of cognitive interests for personality development is that activity in a certain field activates the student's mental processes under the influence of interest. Gives students intellectual satisfaction and emotional upliftment. Interests related to knowledge is a motive that ensures the activity of a person and helps to develop his cognitive activity.

One of the main tasks of primary education is to form interest in fiction in students through reading. This is one of the important issues, and books and reading are of great importance in the education and development of students.

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